

PROCESS EVALUATION FOR THE 8-WEEK READING REMEDIATION: A BASIS FOR ENHANCEMENT

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13335003>

ABSTRACT

This qualitative research study employed phenomenological approach to conduct a process evaluation for the 8-Week Reading Remediation Program in identifying issues and challenges faced by reading teachers and coordinators drawing out proposed improvement to enhance the effectiveness of the program. Based on the findings, the themes derived revealed numerous issues, including insufficient funding, communication gaps, lack of training, limited parental involvement, inadequate monitoring, and implementation deficiencies. As a result, identified themes in the challenges revealed were resource constraints, unfitting materials, scheduling difficulties, teacher-role mismatches, student absenteeism, limited communication, unreliable results, and inconsistent resources. The process evaluation categorized proposed improvement into four components: development focused on securing resources and promoting collaboration, implementation strategies emphasized comprehensive teacher training, schedule adjustments, and elevating reading to a core subject, monitoring initiatives aimed to increase parental involvement and robust program monitoring, and feedback demands consistency to enhance resource quality. The results highlighted the need for substantial program enhancement that provides training on intervention strategies, enhance teachers' skills with localized workshops, develop participatory training programs, implement effective teaching approaches, and examine the effectiveness of localized reading materials.

Keywords: *challenges, enhancement, issues, process evaluation, reading remediation, reading teachers*

INTRODUCTION

Reading is crucial for academic success, as weaknesses in this area hinder learning across disciplines. Remediation of reading inadequacies is vital for reducing educational gaps and enhancing competencies for further education. The prevalence of various reading programs in schools underscores the ongoing significance of reading challenges for learners.

In the global context, Weikert (2018) stressed the importance of reading remediation in addressing learners' unique needs, providing targeted support to prevent long-term academic difficulties and boost confidence. This personalized approach helps close achievement gaps, improve overall academic performance, and align interventions with students' learning styles and preferences to enhance academic success and close learning gaps.

In the Philippines, schools were tasked with fostering proficient readers among students as part of the Department of Education's initiatives like the 3B's Initiative, or "Bawat Bata Bumabasa" (DepEd, 2019). However, the COVID-19 lockdowns have exacerbated the issue of students' reading comprehension nationwide. According to UNICEF, less than 15% of 3 in every 20 learners can read simple texts (de Vera, 2022).

To help struggling readers improve their reading comprehension and prepare for the next grade level in advance of classes during the summer, the Division of Davao City launched the 8-Week Reading Remediation, also known as the 8-Week Reading Curriculum for Struggling Readers (DepEd Davao City, 2021). This program is designed to provide intensive, focused instruction that caters to the individual needs of each student, ensuring they gain the necessary skills to succeed in the upcoming school year.

Despite efforts, the Philippines continues to rank poorly in reading comprehension, placing in the bottom 10 out of 81 countries in the most recent PISA assessment (Servallos, 2023). While there was a slight improvement from being the lowest in 2018 to 76th out of 81 countries in 2022, indicators show a decrease of 4.3 percent in reading comprehension among low-performing students, with no improvement among top-performing students. This ongoing struggle negatively impacts students' academic performance (Southeast Asia Primary Learning Metrics, 2021).

This necessitates further investigation to determine why such issues persist despite the implementation of reading programs. This study also evaluated the effectiveness of the 8-Week Reading Remediation Program by examining the challenges encountered by reading teachers during its implementation. The purpose of this research was to offer recommendations and improvements to enhance the reading program, thereby better addressing the needs of the students.

Research Questions

The research study aimed to explore the issues and challenges received by the reading teachers in the conduct of the 8-week reading remediation program and evaluate its process to seek solutions and improvement. To address the above-cited problem, an answer to the following questions were sought:

1. What are the issues and challenges experienced by the reading teachers in the conduct of the 8-week reading remediation program?
 2. What are the proposed improvement of the 8-week reading remediation program?
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METHODOLOGY

This qualitative study employed phenomenological approach to explore and understand the lived experiences of people and meanings in natural settings, aiming to provide rich descriptions of complex phenomena, albeit often within a limited scope (Casey, 2000). This method was used in this study to identify the issues and challenges faced by the reading teachers in implementing the 8-Week Reading Remediation Program. The results obtained through in-depth interviews were then used to offer improvements to the program.

Sources of Data

For this study, data were gathered via in-depth interviews with six (6) reading teachers from a designated school cluster within the Division of Davao City. Recognizing the importance of ensuring the accuracy and reliability of these insights, the researcher conducted additional in-depth interviews with three (3) reading coordinators from the same school cluster. This approach was taken to validate and corroborate the teachers' experiences, thereby enhancing the credibility and trustworthiness of the study's findings.

In addition, data saturation was met when the responses of the three (3) reading teachers consistently echoed similar themes, which were then affirmed by the reading coordinators, indicating that a comprehensive understanding had been achieved within the qualitative study

Data Gathering Instrument

The researcher used a semi-structured questionnaire during the interviews that consisted of two parts: the first sought to identify problems that arose during the 8-Week Reading Remediation Program implementation, and the second sought suggestions for improving the program's effectiveness.

The first version of the questionnaire had undergone rigorous validation from experts. After pilot testing and inter-rater reliability assessment with a rating of 3.864, the final

version was created. Then, the questionnaire was utilized during the in-depth interviews to identify areas that required improvement and to solicit ideas on addressing the difficulties associated with the 8 - Week Reading Remediation Program being studied.

Sampling Technique

The participants of this study were selected using purposive sampling from the selected schools in one of the clusters in Davao City. The reading teachers and reading coordinators were also purposively selected using a set of criteria to realistically explain the phenomenon that this study wanted to address.

The selection of reading teachers and coordinators adhered to specific criteria: they had to be reading teachers or reading coordinators within the school, with a minimum of three years teaching experience, proficient in Cebuano, Filipino, and English languages, and had consideration of gender diversity. This specific sampling technique was used to emphasize the specific resemblances among participants and their relevance to the research subject (Etikan *et al.*, 2016).

Procedures of the Study

The data collection of this research employed the following steps;

Seeking Approval of the Research Protocol. The researcher ensured approval and guidance for this study from their advisor, technical panel members, and validators before proceeding with the study.

Seeking permission. The submission of letters was the initial stage. To request approval for the required participation, a letter was sent to the Schools Division Superintendent of Davao City. When the letter was accepted, it was sent to the principals of the chosen schools where the research participants who had been identified were situated.

Securing consent from the participants. Signed consent was also obtained from the study participants. They were informed of the research objectives and provided a clear understanding of the research to be conducted. The participants were also informed of their right to withdraw from the study without consequences.

Setting up the interview. The next step was setting the time and place for interviews. The researcher identified the place and time available and convenient for the participants, which was mutually agreed upon by both parties.

Interview proper. The last stage was the interview proper. The participants were informed of the necessary steps to be taken by the researcher, such as recording their responses on a laptop and taking down notes on their responses. The reading teachers were initially interviewed, followed by interviews with the reading coordinators to validate the collected data. The researcher started using in-depth interviews with participants which involved detailed discussions to explore their perspectives, experiences, and insights on a

particular topic or phenomenon (while maintaining professionalism and respect (Eppich *et al.*, 2019)

Gathering and analysis of the data gathered. The digitally recorded in-depth interviews and focus group discussions were transcribed and analyzed. Additionally, the researcher assured the respondents of the confidentiality of these data.

Data Analysis

In analyzing the interviews, the researcher used Thematic Analysis using the seven steps of Colaizzi's Method to systematically treat the qualitative data collected from participants in the 8-Week Reading Remediation Program.

First, was transcribing the audio-recorded interviews. *Second*, was extracting and numbering of transcriptions according to their significance to the study. *Third*, was formulating a more general statement for each significant statement. *Fourth*, was clustering of the codes to form into themes. *Fifth*, was developing of the exhausted descriptions based on the synthesis of all the theme clusters. *Sixth*, was identifying the fundamental structure through a careful analysis of the description of the phenomenon under study. And *seventh*, was returning to the participants for validation of their answers. The final step had ensured that their intended meaning was conveyed in the fundamental structure of the phenomenon and was given opportunity to provide additional information for the inclusion of the final description of the process of the implementation of the 8-Week Reading Remediation Program.

RESULTS

The Issues and Challenges Experienced by Reading Teachers in the Conduct of the 8- Week Reading Remediation Program

Insufficient funding emerged as a significant issue, while the challenge it posed was the reproduction constraint. The issue on lack of participatory planning between reading teachers led to the challenge on use of inappropriate materials, and scheduling conflict further complicated the planning and execution of the program. Additionally, the issue on the lack of training resulted in lack of teacher participation, while the issue on parental involvement deficiency contributed to higher rates of students' absenteeism, exacerbating the challenge of communication barriers. The limited program monitoring posed a big challenge on the fabrication of results; and data-driven improvements which was hampered by the issue on implementation deficiency and resulted in the last identified challenge which was supplement uniformity.

These themes collectively undermined the program's effectiveness and highlighted the need to enhance the efficacy of reading remediation efforts and achieve meaningful improvements in student literacy.

Insufficient Funding

One of the pressing issues in the implementation of the 8-Week Reading Remediation program was insufficient funding. This referred to the inadequacy of financial resources to cover necessary expenses, such as materials, which hindered the reading program's ability to achieve its literacy objectives. Furthermore, this was seen as a major issue in the aspect of program development. Reading teachers A claimed:

“Yes. One of them is that there were no textbooks. As I said, there were no printed materials. We were not able to print individual reading materials. In our case, we lack enough bond papers and photocopiers.” - Reading teacher A

The same supplies were mentioned by Reading teachers C and F. Teachers utilized printers and bond papers to reproduce materials needed for the reading programs. The statements were as follows:

“We need to consider that some schools like us does not have enough allocations for printers, bond papers and inks. It would break the printers if we print everything.” - Reading teacher C

“Our school faced limited resources in terms of materials, and funding for remediation programs. Uhhm these resources involve the production of reading resources such as photocopy machines, inks and bond papers.”- Reading Teacher C

These statements were affirmed by Reading coordinators A and C:

“The problem with the limitation of printing resources. Ang MOOE man gud is budgeted na ba, di sya pwede na mahurot ra for bond papers tanan or pampalit ug photocopier.” [The problem with the limitation of printing resources. The MOOE was already budgeted and it should not be spent entirely for the purchase of bond papers and photocopiers]. - Reading Coordinator A

“Another is again the financial constraints. Limited financial support was given to us that's why we were also limited on the implementation since we just used the given budget.” - Reading Coordinator C

Reproduction Constraint

Because of the issue of insufficient funding, the challenge faced by schools in implementing the program was the time constraint in reproducing the reading materials. Thus, the limited supplies and equipment hindered teachers from adequately catering to each student's needs in terms of the learning resources to be used in the remediation.

The shortage of resources, such as modules and books, necessitated the printing of materials within the school premises. This experience was affirmed by Reading Coordinators A and B, as they stated that:

“We couldn’t find time to print and if we could, wala mi photocopier.” [We couldn’t find time to print and if we could, we don’t have photocopier machines. - Reading Coordinator A)

“Furthermore, there was also a constraint in the reproduction of the reading materials would take hours due to the number of pages and the number of students to be provided.” - Reading Coordinator A

The reading teachers D, and C furthered this claim by mentioning:

“Actually, sir sa printing, wala jud nako nabuhat pud sir na maprint tanan para sa mga bata.” [Actually, in printing, I was not able to print enough for all students] - Reading teacher D

“First, ahh the reading materials itself its already a challenge because its only few, we need to print a lot of modules which takes a lot of time and resources.” - Reading teacher D

One major barrier to offering learning materials to every student in need of remediation was thought to be the time required to reproduce the reading materials. The time required for printing had also interfered with teachers' ability to do their main jobs.

Reading teacher B revealed that:

“If the teachers are the one who provide the materials, magtake pa mi ug time namo magprint mi so mabawasan among time for something else like checking of papers, feedbacking sa essay etc.” [If the teachers are the ones who provide the materials, it will take so much time to print and our time for checking papers, feedback and essays and other activities will be lessened.] - Reading teacher B

Lack of Participatory Planning

Another issue experienced by the reading teachers was the lack of participatory planning in the crafting of the program, that hampered its flexibility to cater to different contexts. Participatory planning entailed the essential involvement of reading teachers in program design, prompted by the challenges encountered during implementation. Reading teacher E strongly supported this by stating:

“ahhm ang implementation mismo sa program sir dapat mahan-ay jud siya ilabi na sa ilahang planning gud sir, lisod man gud kung sila sa taas ang magdesign sa program kay di nila masabtan ang situation ni teacher sa field inig implement. Siguro involvement ni reading coor jud sir sa pagplano sa program.” [The implementation of the program itself needs to be organized especially in the planning. It is really difficult when the program

heads design the program, because they can't understand the situation of the teachers in the field during the implementation. I think the reading coordinators should be part of the program planning.] - Reading teacher E

The lack of participatory planning was a common issue among reading teachers in various schools. They emphasized the need for collaborative planning to create contextualized reading materials and flexible schedules, stating:

“Wala man gud nila giklaro ang instructions sir ba na kita na jud ang mangita ug reading passages na fit sa atong context gud sir.” [The instruction wasn't clear if it was us who will look for reading passages that would fit our context.] - Reading teacher D

“I guess the heads should think of ways on how to solve this problem in schedules like probably making a separate of different way on how to implement this in our schedule as TVE curriculum, but as you know we only accept and implement what is mandated.” - Reading teacher B

These statements underscored the particular difficulties arising from insufficient teacher participation in program planning, notably in the identification of contextualized reading materials. Contextualized teaching and learning in reading comprehension were vital as they facilitated meaningful connections between text and students' lived experiences, thereby enhancing comprehension, retention, and critical analysis skills (Sambayon, et al., 2023).

As affirmed by Reading Coordinator B:

“In terms of strategies, provision of indigenized or localized reading materials provided individually would be the best. However, this could only be achieved if there was a participation of reading teachers and reading coordinators in the crafting of the program.” - Reading Coordinator B

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Inappropriate Materials

Due to the lack of participation in the program planning, one of the major challenges that the reading teacher faced was the deficiency of unified materials that fit the needs of the learners. Consequently, it led to confusion among reading teachers as to what materials to use and their appropriateness for each grade level. This situation was witnessed by Reading teachers D and B who pointed that:

“Wala pud tay kanang coming from the division gani sir na unified na materials. We only had the grade 7 baya sir in the Phil IRI. Kahit na ano sir, kanang from 8-12 diba wlay klaro ang materials. Bisan pa ug pre-test sir lisod. Pareho ra ang 8 and 9 and 10 and 11 so the level of the abilities of the learners dili siya ano.” [We also don’t have a unified material coming from the division. We only have the Grade y Phil IRI. We don’t even have materials for Grade 8-12. Even the pre-test is hard because we use that same material for Grades 8,9,10 and 11. The levels are very different.] - Reading teacher D

“The struggle for the implementation in terms of limitation of resources is that we had to print only the materials in the Phil-IRI but in choosing the materials, we were thinking, “tama aba tong pinili namin? Kaya ba to nang bata?” [The struggle for the implementation in terms of limitation of resources is that we had to print only the materials in the Phil-IRI but in choosing the materials, we were thinking, “Have we chosen the appropriate one? Can the student answer this?]- Reading teacher B

Both reading teachers acknowledged the lack of adequate reading materials for remediation, noting that the Phil IRI manual alone was insufficient. Reading Teacher B further elaborated on this issue, stating:

“Sa Phil IRI mao man jud na ang gina-use pero for me, the result is not that reliable. Dili jud siya reliable sir para sa akoo jud. And then, mao mana ang advise sa atoa na kana ang gamiton, so, mao pud jud na akong ginagamit.” [Phil IRI is what we use but for me, the result is really not reliable for me. Then, that is what was advised for us to use, so that was what I was using.] - Reading teacher E

The coordinator’s experiences highlighted the inadequacy of the provided reading materials to be used in the program. As observed by Reading Coordinator B:

“The main resources that we used were coming from the Phil IRI package. However, the package only has until Grade 7 reading materials. When the program was implemented to include the grade 12, there were no materials readily available to be used or as advised, use the grade 7 for the entire year levels.” - Reading Coordinator

Scheduling Conflict

Another challenge brought by the lack of involvement in program planning was the difficulty in scheduling the reading sessions in the congested curricula where time for reading programs competed with many other subjects for attention, leading to a problem known as “subject congestion,” which negatively affected student engagement. The time and resources needed to carry out reading interventions, successfully, were reduced by this dilemma. This case was noted by Reading Teachers B and E:

“The major issue for the implementation of the intervention programs is actually time. Particularly because the big schools and some schools in cluster 9 are specialized STVE curriculum, so we don’t have vacant time, but the other schools have. I’m not sure how many vacant time the other schools have. In our case, we have the standard subjects plus 2 hours of TVE every day. So that’s from grade 7 up to grade 12. Although we have advisers time, it overlaps my other class for other year level.”- Reading teacher B

“Tech Voc school mi sir and we have ten subjects no sa grade 7 to grade ten. 10 subjects kay naa silay entrep and technical drawing and ICF. So, gamay ra pd mi na teachers.. and then ang klase namo is 7:30 to 4:30 loaded kaayo mi sir.. Naay uban gani over kaayo ilang load especially the Tech Voc ahh katong mga nagtrack ug TVE so loaded kaayo mi and ang implementation mismo sa program si kay medyo maglisod jd ko kay di jd ko

makatouch mismo sa mga teachers because mao lage to loaded kaayo sila.” [Translation: Since we are under technical vocational curriculum, we have 10 subjects from Grade 7 to Grade 10. Ten subjects because we have entrepreneurship and Technical Drawing and our classes are from 7:30 am to 4:30 pm. We are heavily loaded with subjects. This hinders the implementation of the program because I can’t ask for help from other teachers because the other teachers are loaded with subjects] - Reading teacher E

Both reading teachers from a school with a Tech Voc Curriculum highlighted the difficulty of finding time to implement the program due to overloaded subjects and a congested schedule. Reading Teacher D expanded on this, emphasizing the schedule conflicts caused by overlapping activities. Reading Teacher D shared:

“Sa karung face to face sir, medyo overlapping na jud ang activities sir ba. So ang gibuhang namo, wala jud namo to naimplement sir. Because it’s hard for us to insert the reading activities because we have 10 subjects baya sir.” [Now that we are having face to face, there were overlapping activities. That’s why we were not able to implement the program, because it’s hard for us to insert the reading activities because we have ten subjects] - Reading teacher D

The time constraints also mentioned by the reading coordinators in the STVE Curricula and the overlapping activities had made it difficult to include in the schedule the Reading Remediation Program. As affirmed by Reading Coordinators A and B:

“Pero kung ako ang pabut-on, cguro need nato pangitaan ug schedule ang remediation diri sa school ilabi na kay ang head sa reading wala siguro kahibalo sa cases nato di sa TechVoc schools.” [If I were to decide, we really need to find schedules for remediation especially that our reading head does not know our situation in Tech Voc schools. - Reading Coordinator A

“I think the biggest problem is the schedule. The program was implemented during summer and was later inserted during the school year. However, it was difficult to focus only in reading because teachers have numerous subjects to teach. - Reading Coordinator B

Lack of Training

The insufficient training of reading teachers was a major issue that many reading teachers faced during the program's implementation. The lack of training denoted an absence of systematic instruction or preparation in a particular skill or knowledge area essential to the conduct of reading programs. During implementation, reading coordinators observed this circumstance, as Reading Coordinators A and C disclosed:

“One thing is the training. Most reading teachers lack training in the conduct of the program because only the coordinators were required to join and they were on online format.” - Reading Coordinator A

“It would be more effective I think if all teachers are engaged and trained with the necessary skills in implementing the program.” - Reading Coordinator C

These statements accentuated the challenges faced by the reading teachers in the lack of training in the reading program implementation. This resulted in limited training for the teachers under their care. Reading teacher E noted that:

“Kanang ako sir kulang jud ko anang training para maimplement nako tarung ang program. Kanang kulang ko ug dapat jud ko matrain unsay mga pamaagi para mahan-ay despite sa mga challenges ug mga issues na muface nato as reading ano coordinator.” [There must be trainings. I admit that I lack training to implement the program properly. I am really lacking and I need the training on the ways on how to implement the program properly despite the issues and challenges that we face as reading coordinators.] - Reading teacher E

Reading Teacher E emphasized the need for training, admitting that this was a skill she lacked in the program's implementation. Other teachers expanded on this, highlighting that training was essential for establishing a clear direction and vision for the implementation:

“There was no proper training on our end on how to implement or, where to start ahhm what to do with the materials. The materials were provided but we were tasked to choose on our own accord but the problem was again there was no ahh orientation on the timeline on when was the exact date to begin, how to proceed with it, ahmm the papers that should be done with it.” - Reading Teacher B

“Lastly, we need to be properly guided on the implementation through a more comprehensive and teacher training for reading coordinators. I think this will prevent us from being lost in the process.” -Reading Teacher A

Teacher's Participation

The limited number of reading teachers as program implementers in schools necessitated participation from other teachers to get involved. However, their lack of expertise brought challenges due to their limitations. Undoubtedly, in fostering a holistic approach to literacy development, the involvement of non-language teachers in the reading program gave a huge challenge in enhancing students' overall literacy skills. Consequently, the absence of training among participating teachers uncovered their reluctance to engage, stemming from apprehensions about making mistakes and a lack of preparedness. Reading teachers D and B made a strong claim about this as they revealed:

“Ang teachers pud, one of the science teachers approached me. Willing to help man si Mam. But when she implemented the reading materials na gihatag, na-correct man siya sa bata sa pronunciation. Giduol ko niya “kanang Mam” kanang sorry jud kayo. Gusto jud ko mutabang pero lahi man jud no? Thankful ko kay mam kay willing jud kayo mutabang si mam. Nakatawa lage siya kay ang bata nagcorrect niya. Mao to, wla na siya

nagpadayun.” [As for the teachers, one of the Science teachers approached me. She was willing to help, but when she implemented the reading material given to them, she was corrected by the student in pronunciation. She approached me and said, “Ma’am, I am really sorry. I really want to help but this is really different.” I am thankful for her willingness to help. She even laughed that a student corrected her. So that was the reason why she didn’t continue.] - Reading teacher D,

“Hindi man ako English teacher, hindi man ako Filipino major, pano ko yan gagawin?” Or How am I going to do that when that’s not my major or I don’t specialize on that?” [I’m not an English teacher, I’m not a Filipino major, how would I do that? Or How am I going to do that when that’s not my major or I don’t specialize on that?] - Reading teacher B

The hesitation from non-language teachers to become reading teachers reflected their lack of expertise in the field, highlighting the disparity in their skills. Additionally, the heavy workloads and limited number of school personnel further constrained their participation. As Reading Teacher C shared:

“We have limited time and personnel. In our case as a newly established school, we only have few teachers. That means that we handle numerous subjects. I think that was the main reason why most of them are not really into this program because it would be an extra burden for them.” - Reading teacher C

Training was very important for the teachers to implement the program effectively. Because of the limited number of language teachers in a school, non-language teachers were asked to assist, consequently causing slip-ups in the implementation, hesitation, and confusion. Furthermore, to meet the needs of the teachers who would carry out the program, it became clear that all needed to receive training. But this problem was exacerbated by time constraints and the lack of initiatives by the personnel in the Department. As confirmed by the Reading Coordinators A, B, and C;

“Ang uban medyo naa pud hesitance na mujoin kay dili lage sila kabalo sa program pud.” [Others are hesitant to join because they also don’t know how to implement it.] - Reading Coordinator A

“I understand the case of the teachers that they were already bombarded with tasks, ancillaries and deadlines.” - Reading Coordinator B

“Because we are all reading teachers. Whatever subject matter you are focused on, we are all considered as reading teachers and we are all capable of teaching our students the skill of reading.” - Reading Coordinator C

Parental Involvement Deficiency

One other aspect of the reading program's implementation that was thought to have contributed to the myriads of issues was the deficiency in parental involvement. This referred to the active participation and engagement of parents or guardians in their

children's educational activities, including but not limited to school events, homework assistance, and communication with teachers (Iroegbu and Igweike, 2020). However, the lack of parental participation in the monitoring of students' progress in reading intervention was perceived as a great issue. This condition was also witnessed by Reading Coordinators B and C:

"In terms of monitoring their progress at home, it was really difficult because of the absence of involvement of parent in their child's learning progress." - Reading Coordinator B

"Parental support was also limited during the program. Some parents were not responsive when they were asked to get the reading materials in school." - Reading Coordinator C

The statements of the coordinators confirmed the need for improvement in the participation of parents during the remediation program. It was undeniable that parents should be seen as partners with teachers in fostering student success through collaborative efforts to support academic, social, and emotional development (Lekli and Kaloti, 2015). This difficulty was noted by the reading teachers A, and F as they declared:

"I think the very first thing is the parent's participation. Parents need to monitor their children's progress and guide them in reading at home and refrain them from frequently using their phones." - Reading Teacher A

"Siguro because sa ilang balay jud walay follow up reading from parents and guardians so lisod jud kayo." [Maybe the difficulty was because at home, there was no follow up of their reading tasks from parents and guardians] - Reading teacher E

These statements highlighted the need for more participation from parents in the reading progress of their child. Furthermore, parents had to understand and perform their part in watching over and supporting their children at home (Tomas et al., 2021). This was furthered by Reading Teacher F in her claim that:

"...lack of parental involvement or support from parents to provide guidance to the activities provided to students under remediation." - Reading teacher F

Student's absenteeism

The issue in the lack of parental guidance resulted in a challenge in the student's presence during the program implementation, which affected the consistent participation and had impeded learning outcomes. The persistent or prolonged absence of students from school led to missed opportunities for participating in activities aimed at addressing their reading problems. Dismally, students who should be participating in reading remediation had the highest number of absences during its conduct. The Reading teachers A and D identified this problem and expressed that:

“One of them is the students’ absenteeism, because not all students are present during the conduct of the reading activities. To add, most of the students who are in need of improvement are the ones who are frequently absent.” - Reading teacher A

“But the problem sir is no participation due to absences kay luoy pud sila sir ba. They came from a kanang luoy na family. ... xxx ... Ang problema wala man pud cooperation sir uy.” [But the problem is no participation due to absences because of their situation at home. They came from a poor family. ... xxx ... However, I don’t see and cooperation from them.] - Reading teacher D

The reading teachers’ statements emphasized the presence of the students targeted for remediation since reading was a nonstop process of enhancement. In cases where students were sent materials to work on them at home, Reading Teacher E experienced an almost similar dilemma.

“And syempre the long time problem nato which is the absenteeism. Lisod jud sir kay if padad-an ug module di mu-answer. Karun na face-to-face na, di muskwela. Mao jud ni ang struggle sa pagpabasa sa ilaha kay wala man sila.” [and of course, our long-time problem in absenteeism. ..xxx, because when you send them modules, they won’t answer. Now in face-to-face, they won’t go to school. This is the struggle in letting them read and they are not around.] - Reading teacher E

Reading Coordinators A and B confirmed these statements by stating that:

“The primary factor siguro is the absences of the students. Most students jud na kelangan ug remediation sa reading were mostly absent.” [Maybe the primary factor is absenteeism. Most students who are in need of remediation were the ones mostly absent.] - Reading Coordinator A

“However, most were really a problem due to absenteeism. It was really a problem because we needed to provide help for them but the problem is that they were not always in school.” - Reading Coordinator B

Communication Barriers

Monitoring learners' progress in the conduct of the program was seen as a prevalent issue. The barriers to communication referred to the restricted ability to connect and interact due to the absence or unreliability of mobile devices, cellular signals, and Wi-Fi access. In the context of the 8-Week Reading Remediation Program, monitoring the students’ progress with the assistance of the parents enabled teachers to tailor instruction, identify areas needing improvement, and ultimately enhance literacy skills effectively. Nevertheless, reaching these students posed a challenge due to human resource limitations and time constraints. Reading teachers B and D strongly claimed that:

“Majority of the problem was logistic issue. We can’t locate them, we can't reach them and we have difficulty in trying to find them because we don’t have enough people or even time to reach them particularly because teachers already have enough on their plate.” -Reading teacher B

“I tried also sir kanang mag messenger. I let them record their ano activity in reading. Syempre katong musend lng pud ato, those students na mga good students. Sila lang pud ang nagcomply pero katong students na belong to frustration jud very hard for us to reach out the learners.” [I tried to use the messenger app. I let them record their activity in reading. Of course, only those students who are already good were the ones active in submission. Those who belong to the frustration level are very hard to reach out] - Reading teacher D

These statements highlighted the issue in communicating with the learners in terms of sending the materials and tracking their progress. Tracing students' progress was vital as it provided insights into their learning outcomes and developmental journey (Yang and Li, 2018). Reading Coordinator A expanded this by stating:

“We couldn’t reach most of the students and track on their learning progress because most of the students have no cellphones. There were some who had pero [but] mostly walay [no] signal or wifi.” - Reading Teacher A

Reading Coordinators A and C also witnessed this scenario, as they affirmed:

“Another big factor was when this program was conducted during the summer vacation, we couldn’t reach most of the students and track on their learning progress because most of the students have no cellphones. There were some who had pero mostly wala [no] signal or wifi. That’s the biggest factor I think.” -Reading Coordinator A

“The worst case was when we couldn’t reach the learners. I think it was due to the fact that they don’t have cellphones or they lack internet connections at home.” -Reading Coordinator C

Limited Program Monitoring

The lack of effective mechanisms on program monitoring on the learning progress served as a major hurdle in the reading remediation program implementation which contributed to the challenge in the establishment of efficient monitoring schemes. Inadequate monitoring by school administrators or authorities impeded teachers' ability to gauge program’s effectiveness and students' progress. Reading coordinators, as one of the key channels for receiving instructions, even highlighted this situation. According to Reading Coordinator B:

“So far, like what I could notice, the supervising head would only be active during the pretest and post-test. I think the presence of the program heads in terms of constant

updating and monitoring would provide a more effective implementation.” - Reading Coordinator B

Similarly, reading teachers B and E emphasized the importance of constant monitoring in the implementation of the reading remediation program, highlighting the ineffectiveness of executing tasks without proper oversight:

“We’re honestly feeling a bit lost in the process in all honesty. I guess, although I need to understand the part of the heads that it does take time and resources to do the follow up and the meetings but we’re doing this for the students and we want to make a good effort and a good work with a certain standard so I guess if it will cost you that much.” - Reading teacher B

“Implement the program with constant progress monitoring kay useless jud kaayo kung nakaimplement ta ug program pero dili kaayo nato sya inana ka namonitor so dapat mamonitor jud ta kung tama ba ni atong ginabuhay sa atong program.” [We need to implement the program with constant progress monitoring because it is useless to implement a program without monitoring if the tasks in the program were properly executed.] - Reading teacher E

With a similar claim, Reading Teacher D suggested:

“Kana gud sa mga higher level authorities. Magsabot sila ba. Katong nagvisit si EPS diri arun makita pud nila ang sitwasyon and matabangan nila labi na sa schedule namo.” [In the case of the higher-level authorities. They should talk about this. Like the visit of the EPS here in our school to see our situation and to be given help especially in our schedule.] - Reading teacher D

Fabrication of Results

The lack of program monitoring posed a challenge in providing trustworthy assessment outcomes, hence the question of its reliability. The shortage of teachers and the number of tasks that reading teachers were given forced the coordinators to provide reports that were just made made-up. Hence, it was difficult for them to firmly implement the reading remediation program. With this, the Reading Teacher C disclosed:

“Whether we like it or not most of them do this only for the implementation itself, but it's up to us to make-up the results.” - Reading teacher C

This full disclosure of reading teachers in the falsification of data highlighted their desperation to accomplish a task, compromising its truthfulness. Though it might seem demoralizing, Reading Teachers E and A furthered:

“...it hard, I only make up results in Filipino and base it on the results in English” -Reading teacher E

“There were cases pa gani na padad-an namo ug reading materials pero wala jud gihapon giansweran. If maansweran man, di pud mi sure if sila ba nag answer.” [There were instances when we sent reading materials to learners, but they were not completed. Even when the materials were returned, we couldn't be certain if the learners themselves had answered them]. -Reading Coordinator A

The Reading Coordinators were well aware of this situation. However, they only grasped the full extent of it due to the heavy workload faced by the reading teachers. This was confirmed by Reading Coordinator B who stated:

“Admittedly, I even understand that sometimes we needed to just create data for compliance because we had no choice due to the numerous deadlines and activities.” - Reading Coordinator B

Implementation Deficiency

Another issue was the implementation deficiency due to ineffective execution of the program. In addition, this deficiency was primarily due to a lack of feedback, hindering the ability to assess progress and make necessary adjustments. The Reading Teachers C and B indicated that:

“One more thing is that the division should provide us feedback at the end of the implementation for us to reflect on the result and for them to know our struggles. You see what happened, instead of addressing our struggles, they even added more grade levels during the following year, that's why proper feedbacking is really essential.” - Reading teacher C

“ang implementation ngayon is based on reports and if the implementation is done, yes or no, how did you do it but there is no word on dapat ganito ang ginawa mo there is no feedback so, as teachers you know that feedback is important and that is what we are short of from our division coordinator.” [The implementation now is based on reports and if the implementation is done, yes or no?. How did you do it? There were no words like “This is what you should have done”. there was no feedback. As teachers you know that feedback is important and that is what we are short of from our division coordinator.] - Reading teacher B

These statements stressed the need for constant feedback. The reading teachers emphasized this to receive improvement; thus, Reading Teacher E added:

“..and dapat pud siguro after nila magmonitor makabalo pud ta if namao ba ni atong mga trabaho kay arun maimprove gud ta sir and they will know ba our difficulties para ma-address nila. No words man gud ba.” [After the monitoring, we should know if our work was right in order to improve and for them to know our difficulties so they would address them] - Reading teacher E

As highlighted by Reading Teacher E, feedback from the DepEd Division at the end of program implementations was crucial for reflection and addressing challenges. Without

it, the issues persisted, as seen with the perennial matters of additional grade levels and unresolved reading struggles. This called for the necessity of effective feedback mechanisms for reading program improvement. Reading Coordinator A revealed more about the problem by stating that:

“Isa pa, I need pud communication from the program supervisor. So far, wala may feedback sa amoa pud regarding sa unsaon namo pagtabang amoa reading teachers.” [one more thing, I need communication from the program supervisor. So far, there were no feedback to us on how to help our reading teachers.] - Reading Coordinator A

Implementation Uniformity

Due to the issue of implementation deficiency, it resulted to a challenge on supplement inconsistency. Program heads should provide directives to teachers that align with the program objectives, empowering them to adapt strategies based on student needs to maximize the program's impact on literacy development. However, the inconsistency of instructions and directives from program heads to teachers led to confusion, irregularities in implementation, and reduced effectiveness of the reading program. This was true even in the uniformity of materials to be used. Reading coordinator B elaborated:

“We have no standard or uniform reading materials. It was the burden of the teachers to look for them which suits the level of the learners.” - Reading Coordinator B

The participants also highlighted the lack of unified instructions and materials for implementing the reading program, leading to discrepancies in schedules, directives, and resources across different grade levels. Reading Teachers A and D expounded on this by stating that:

“There should also be a unified instruction regarding this implementation, because we didn't have the same schedule, instruction and reading materials. This is understandable because we have different schedule of classes.” - Reading Teacher A

“Wala pud tay kanang coming from the division gani sir na unified na materials. We only had the grade 7 baya sir in the Phil IRI. Kahit na ano sir, kanang from 8-12 diba wlay klaro ang materials na gamiton.” [We also don't have unified reading materials to use coming from the Division. We only had Grade 7 coming from the Phil IRI. There were no clear instructions on what to use for the Grade 8-12.] - Reading teacher D

The reading teachers stated the need for unified reading materials to cater to the needs of the learners in every grade level. Similarly, Reading Teacher B demanded for uniformity in templates for monitoring students' progress, as she stated:

“Although it might seem that it can be done on our own initiative, ahmm, We kind of need the templates for recording the scores, although we can do it by ourselves, but it would be effective if we have a uniform way of monitoring students' progress.” -Reading teacher B

The Proposed Improvement to Enhance the 8-Week Reading Remediation Program

In the context of the program implementation in the cluster 9, SOP 1 revealed the issues and challenges that the reading teachers experienced during the implementation. It highlighted the need to address these hurdles to enhance the program holistically. These identified issues and challenges formed the basis for proposing solutions, which were categorized under the four components of process evaluation: Development, Implementation, Monitoring, and Feedback. The concentration was to get the proposed solutions based on the identified challenges in SOP 1 as suggested by the participants.

Resource Availability

In the first SOP, the discussion emphasized the challenges faced by reading teachers regarding the accessibility of reading materials in implementing the program. These concerns pertained to the program's development phase, which included issues related to the availability, reproduction, and lack of standardized reading resources. It was emphasized that the availability of diverse reading resources was essential for fostering a successful reading program, as it provided students with access to a wide range of texts catering to their interests and reading levels. In terms of addressing this issue, Reading teachers B and E suggested:

“... the provision of materials. I think we can, kaya man siguro na gumawa na lang kami ng libro na hindi kami yung magprint, like kanang mga procured na books so it would really help if the students had their reading materials not from printed bond paper but hardbound” [...the provision of materials. I think we can make a book that we are not the ones who will print like procured books. It would really help if the students had their reading materials not from printed bond paper but hardbound] - Reading teacher B

“I think the provision of reading materials gud sir. Kanang dili na mi magprint ba or kanang naay books gud na ipanghatag sa school sir. Mas sayon na siya na paagi for us.” [I think there should be provision of reading materials like books to be given in school so that we won't need to print. It would be lighter for us.] - Reading Teacher E

The participants saw the importance of physical books being used by students rather than reading materials printed on ordinary bond paper. Students wanted to hold books in their hands, therefore, having printed reading materials available was vital (Elmarash and Mokhtar, 2023). Further, Reading Teacher F highlighted the use of a modern solutions:

“Investing in technology resources such as educational software, digital literacy tools, and online learning platforms, providing a wide range of print and digital materials, including leveled readers, decodable texts, audiobooks, and digital libraries, can support differentiated instruction and engage students with diverse interests and reading abilities.” - Reading Teacher F

The statements emphasized the significance of investing in a variety of technology resources, including print and non-print materials, to support differentiated instruction and engage students with diverse reading materials to ignite their interests. Reading coordinators also identified a shortage of materials as a significant challenge, prompting them to suggest solutions to address this issue. Reading Coordinator A and C claimed:

“Isa pa is the materials to be used. Unta naa na para print na lang ta.”[One more thing is the materials to be uses. I hope they are already available for us to just print directly.] - Reading Coordinator A

“Another is creating the materials digital or printed that are more suitable to the learners and not just mere stories, but text materials that students could relate, they may add pictures that are colorful and attractive.” - Reading Coordinator C

Program Collaboration

The challenge of addressing the gap in program planning was highlighted in the initial SOP as it consequently affected the appropriateness of materials to be used and the scheduling conflicts if the implementation. This not only targeted the essential aspect of the program that needed to be addressed but also provided solutions to contextual issues. This was strongly remarked by reading teachers D and E who stated:

“And siguro dapat naay actual planning jud sir na involved ang reading teachers or bisan ang principals sir to identify lang ang mga issues in the program and address them accordingly.” [Maybe there should be actual planning that involves the reading teachers and principals to identify issues in the program and address them accordingly] - Reading teacher D

“...lisod man gud kung sila sa taas ang magdesign sa program, kay di nila masabtan ang situation ni teacher sa field inig implement. Siguro involvement ni reading coor jud sir sa pagplano sa program. [It’s difficult when only the heads are involved in the design of the program because they won’t understand our situation during the implementation in the field. Maybe there should be involvement of the reading coordinator in the planning of the program] - Reading teacher E

Meanwhile, Reading Teacher A stressed the representation of teachers in the actual planning in her statement:

“I think we as teachers or there should be a representative to represent us in the planning of the program. especially that we need a reading material that is fit for the students’ level and that it should be interesting and engaging to students.” -Reading teacher A

The reading teachers emphasized the importance of teacher collaboration in program design, which enhanced understanding of student needs and instructional strategies, leading to personalized interventions for diverse learners. This was attested by the Reading Coordinators A and B who affirmed that:

“Siguro ang hinungdan ani is walay participation sa atong mga reading coordinators sa crafting sa program. This way we can design programs and materials na suited sa atoa learners and sa atoa mga context. [Maybe the cause of the problem is that there was no participation of the reading coordinators in the crafting of the program. This way we can design programs suited for our learners context.] - Reading Coordinator A

“In terms of strategies, provision of indigenized or localized materials provided individually would be the best. However, this could only be achieved if there was a participation of reading teachers and reading coordinators in the crafting of the program.” -Reading Coordinator B

Teachers' Training

Providing teacher training during the Implementation stage enhanced the competence of reading teachers, reduced errors made by non-language teachers, and boosted their participation in the program. These measures addressed the challenges identified in the initial SOP.

Implementing comprehensive teacher training programs was essential to enhancing the effectiveness of a reading program by equipping educators with the necessary skills and strategies to address diverse learner needs and facilitate optimal student engagement and progress. However, during implementation, this was the main difficulty the coordinators had to deal with. As proposed by Reading Coordinators A and B:

“One thing is the training. Most reading teachers lack training in the conduct of the program because only the coordinators were required to join and they were on online format.” - Reading Coordinator A

“Training is the biggest need that our reading teachers need especially in the implementation of this program. we need to capacitate our reading teachers.” - Reading Coordinator B

The necessity for personnel training depended on their ability to effectively adapt to diverse learner needs during assessment and remediation, as emphasized Reading Teachers C and E:

“Training for the personnel of course that’s they need also enough training to be able to ahh adjust to the different kinds of learners that they are going to assess and that needs remediation.” - Reading Teacher C

“In terms of teacher ahh investing in teacher training... There should be teacher training.” - Reading teacher E

As stated by Reading Teacher C and E, there should be proper training for teachers to cater to the reading needs of learners. Reading Teacher B supported this proposition in her statement:

“The key issue here is on the number one, training, and it should be done in person, because if online which was done before, there are a lot of problems. There will be a lot of confusions and a lot will be hesitant to ask in zoom meetings., So there is a lot of miscommunications that happens when the inquiry is done online so ahmm. Number one issue is, there has to be proper training and it should be done in person.” - Reading teacher B

As proposed by the Reading Coordinators B and D:

“I can only think of utilizing the monthly SLAC sessions. So if we maximize our SLAC and find a way to address the ahmm learning concerns of the students, which is kind of rooted in reading, then we can make it a reading session and maybe do reading a way to do the intervention trainings in between the SLAC session.” - Reading teacher B

“For the SLAC session, make it clear to them what is the program all about, unsay (what) target and goals. The process.” - Reading teacher D

This addressed the common issue of teachers' insufficient training for both language and non-language teacher who implemented the 8-Week Reading Remediation Program. Reading teachers B and A supported this by stating:

“I think this can be done in the school level, like training all reading teachers whether they are language or non-language teachers. We can use the SLAC sessions and invite some speakers” - Reading Coordinator B

“Trainings for reading teachers for the basics of reading to share to other teachers through roll-out sessions or SLAC sessions.” - Reading Coordinator A

Through utilizing School Learning Action Cell sessions, reading teachers could promote a common goal. This enabled them to acknowledge the differences in teaching language and non-language subjects and work together with non-language teachers to teach reading in classrooms (Haukas et al., 2022). Through collaborative inquiry, educators could identify contextual challenges, explore innovative approaches, and implement evidence-based solutions to enhance the quality of education (DO 35, s. 2016). Although the main differentiation was formed within each topic's framework, the outcome of SLAC sessions might be used to integrate reading through subject integration. Reading Teachers A and B suggested:

“I think the best strategy is integrating reading in all subjects. I really believe reading can be integrate in all subjects. I think students will improve when they make reading habit, for example in mathematics or science. Then the teacher will ask questions regarding the texts read from their lessons. I think this is an effective strategy to enhance the reading of the students. - Reading Teacher A

“Then the outcome of the SLAC would be for teachers to make an effort and integrate in their daily teaching the reading strategies that have been learned in the sessions.” - Reading teacher B

Adjustment of Schedules

The congestion of the curriculum was seen as a huge challenge in the Implementation stage. This was especially because half of the respondents belong to a Strengthened Technical Vocational Education (STVE) Curriculum where 8 subjects were taught within the day.

The development of reading programs necessitated modifications to class scheduling, which provided flexibility and ideal learning environments. It also enabled educators to allocate sufficient time for reading interventions. Therefore, the participants emphasized that the program supervisors should find workable ways to implement the reading intervention and incorporate it into the class schedule for protected time in cases where schools implementing with congested curricula such as the Strengthened Technical Vocational Education (STVE) strand. Reading teachers D and A suggested:

“Sa case sa mga heads sir, sa akua lang sir. Tech-Voc man mi sir. kabalo man sila na 10 subjects. Siguro kanang mahan-ay unta among schedule. Kanang naa jud time na mapasok namo ang reading.” [In the case of the heads, as for me, since we are Tech-Voc, they know that we have 10 subjects. Maybe they need to arrange the schedules to have time to include reading.] - Reading teacher D

“Pero kung ako ang pabut-on, cguro need nato pangitaan ug schedule ang remediation diri sa school ilabi na kay ang head sa reading wala siguro kahibalo sa cases nato di sa TechVoc schools.” [If I were to decide, we really need to find schedules for remediation especially that our reading head does not know our situation in Tech Voc schools. - Reading Coordinator A

Similarly, Reading Teacher C added:

“Considering that there a lot students that need to be assessed and the limited and overlapping activities, so I guess that it is better to move this program back to the summer vacation. To provide more focus for students in improving their reading.” - Reading teacher C

Furthermore, the implementation of the program during the school year was seen as a struggle as it overlapped with other school activities. Reading Coordinator B also provided a similar solution to the issue:

“As for the scheduling conflict, since we really couldn’t insert this program, I think its better to move it back during summer.” - Reading Coordinator B

Reading as a Subject

To radically address the need to provide a schedule for intervention due to a congested curriculum, the reading teachers also proposed to make reading a standalone subject. This theme advocated for the formal incorporation of reading as a separate subject within educational curricula, emphasizing its critical role in fostering literacy skills and academic success. Reading teachers D and E suggested that:

“Naa untay one hour sir na magabsa lang jud ang bata. Or himuon sya na subject para matutukan jud ang reading kay kung i-insert-insert lang ang English nimo four days, i-insert nimo diha nag-apas pa ko sa competencies. Kay kulang jud.” [There should be an hour that the students will read or make it a subject to have reading as a focus. Because if you only insert it in your four days of classes, it won't be enough.] - Reading teacher D

“I-consider siya as load para naa jud syay schedule or time na para jud ma ano jud ang reading. Murag ibutang jud sya as subject jud sya. Kay mao man gud na ang pinaka-foundation sa mga students.” [Consider it as a load for it to have a schedule or time to address reading. Maybe make it as a subject, because that is the very foundation of students.] - Reading teacher E

The statements of the reading coordinators proposed to elevate the status of reading by advocating for it to be a stand-alone subject, emphasizing the crucial need for dedicated focus and resources on developing literacy skills. Reading Teacher B added:

“But if if the schedule won't be moved to the summer, I'd probably go with making it a single load sir or dedicate really a period that student's main focus is really reading.” - Reading Teacher B

As affirmed by Reading Coordinator A:

“.. or if pwede one load na lang ning reading especially for struggling readers jud.” [If possible, we make reading a teaching load especially for struggling readers] - Reading Coordinator A

Parental Involvement

Parental engagement in reading initiatives was pivotal for children's literacy growth. As outlined in the initial SOP, parental involvement played a vital role in monitoring the program to ensure active participation and attendance of learners during implementation, given that absenteeism posed a significant challenge to the program's implementation.

Delving deeper, collaborative efforts between parents and English teachers significantly influenced children's reading proficiency and attitudes, underscoring the necessity of actively involving parents in the program. In order to achieve students' reading achievements, the reading teachers recognized this as a significant barrier in the first SOP and emphasized the crucial role that parents should play in cooperating with and

supporting school reading programs. As attested and proposed by Reading Coordinators B and C:

“When the program was conducted during the summer, the parents play a big role in terms of guiding and helping the child at home. However, when the program was conducted in school, the role of the parent was to make sure that the learners were present. “ - Reading Coordinator B

“One more thing is the support coming from parents because they too have a big part in improving their child’s reading abilities in terms of guidance and monitoring of progress.”
- Reading Coordinator C

With their firsthand experience, they observed this situation. As suggested by Reading teacher A and F:

“Parents need to monitor their children’s progress and guide them in reading at home and refrain them from frequently using their phones.” -Reading teacher A

“For me, engaging families as partners in the reading remediation process by providing resources, workshops, and support for promoting literacy at home.” -Reading teacher F

As highlighted by the reading teachers, parental involvement in the program directly affects their child's performance and participation, underscoring the necessity for enhanced parental support. This need was reinforced by Reading Teacher D, who expressed:

“Dapat man gud naa jud cooperation ang parents sir kay sila ma magbantay ug mutudlo sa bata sa balay kay we consider them as partners baya.” [There should be cooperation among parents because they will provide guidance and assistance at home and we consider them as partners.] - Reading teacher D

Regular Program Monitoring

The challenge in the absence of regular monitoring, as stated in the first SOP, resulted in questionable assessment results. Thus, this was seen as a vital solution to address reading program issues by providing ongoing assessment and adjustment to ensure the effectiveness of interventions. This was observed by reading teachers A and E who recommended:

“There should also be monitoring in schools or clusters to check the implementation. Though it may be scary to some especially when program heads would come and visit, I think it is very important to provide technical assistance to reading teachers.” -Reading teacher A

“Implement the program with constant progress monitoring kay useless jud kaayo kung nakaimplement ta ug program pero dili kaayo nato sya inana ka namonitor so dapat mamonitor jud ta kung tama ba ni atong ginabuhay sa atong program.” [We need to implement the program with constant progress monitoring because it is useless to

implement a program without monitoring if the tasks in the program were properly executed.] - Reading teacher E

While the reading teachers acknowledged the numerous responsibilities of the program supervisor, they emphasized the essential presence of the supervisor. Reading Teacher B noted:

“I understand he has overlapping responsibilities but ahh it’s a big task to lead reading coordinators of the high School unit particularly because we have non-readers in high school. He should be there with us. So, he has to constantly update us.” - Reading teacher B

The reading teachers articulated a favorable reception to the monitoring initiative by program leaders while also acknowledging the prevailing culture of apprehension among teachers during such engagements. With this, Reading Coordinator B also had a similar proposition:

“I think, I would recommend that there is a need to provide constant monitoring to us coordinators so that we can relay them to our reading teachers.” -Reading Coordinator B

Consistency of Feedback

One of the emphasized challenges encountered in executing the reading program was the presence of feedback from program heads. Participants underscored this as a significant factor in verifying the accuracy of program implementation. Consistent feedback from program heads in the reading program ensures a steady flow of guidance and evaluation for teachers, contributing to ongoing improvement and alignment with program objectives. As stated by reading teachers B and E:

“First is of course the guidance and the follow through and feedbacks from our heads ... it could be of great help so feedback from the heads would be a wonderful start.” - Reading teacher B

“...dapat pud siguro after nila magmonitor makabalo pud ta if namao ba ni atong mga trabaho kay arun maimprove gud ta sir and they will know ba our difficulties para ma-address nila. No words man gud ba.” [After monitoring, maybe they should tell us if our implementation was right for us to improve and for them to know our struggles for it to be addressed. There were really no words about it.] - Reading teacher E

Reading Teacher C added:

“One more thing is that the division should provide us feedback at the end of the implementation for us to reflect on the result and for them to know our struggles.” - Reading teacher C

The guidance, follow-through, and feedback from program heads were vital components that could greatly support the implementation of the 8-Week Reading Program, receiving feedback from program heads was an essential starting point for improvement. Reading Coordinator A attested this by stating that:

“Isa pa, I need pud communication from the program supervisor. So far, wala may feedback sa amoa pud regarding sa unsaon namo pagtabang amoa reading teachers sa ilahang mga problems sa pagconduct sa program.” [one more thing, I need communication from the program supervisor. So far, there was no feedback regarding how to help my reading teachers on how to cope with the problems in the program.] - Reading Coordinator A

DISCUSSION

The Issues and Challenges Experienced by Reading Teachers in the Conduct of the 8- Week Reading Remediation Program

Insufficient Funding

The accessibility and utilization of reading materials played a pivotal role in enhancing reading proficiency by affording learners exposure to a breadth of textual contexts, styles, and subject matters. Such exposure fostered the development of critical reading skills, fluency, and comprehension abilities, constituting fundamental components of literacy acquisition and cognitive development (Omuna et al., 2016). Similarly, allocating a budget for reading programs was crucial as it ensured the provision of necessary resources and support systems to foster literacy development and educational equity (Knight et al., 2016).

The fact that there was insufficient funding for reading materials in schools, even with budget allocations from Maintenance and Other Operating Expenses, or MOOE, was another urgent issue. MOOE pertained to a spending category aimed at supporting the operational needs of government agencies, encompassing expenses related to supplies, transportation, travel, utilities such as water and power, and repairs (DepEd Order No. 8, s.2019). However, due to either limited funding or insufficient budget allocation specifically designated for instructional materials, this provision was deficient to cover the costs of printing instructional materials or purchasing books.

Needless to say, to fund or allocate a budget to meet the requirements for reading resources and other basic needs, teachers had to be involved in the process. They get money out of their pockets to placate their instructional needs (Ochada and Gempes, 2018). Other nations, such as Tanzania, experienced a similar scarcity of educational resources, with textbooks, reference books, and other school supplies being unavailable

(Liyomo et al., 2017). Similar to Nigeria, where funding was insufficient, there were also not enough educational resources (Uzuegbu et al., 2013).

Reproduction Constraint

It was highlighted that the teachers faced difficulty in finding time to reproduce reading materials due to their already extensive workload. In the Philippine public school system, educators were allotted a teaching load of six hours, supplemented by an additional two hours designated for pedagogical activities encompassing lesson preparation, assessment, and documentation of academic progress (DepEd Order 5, 2024).

Nevertheless, within the milieu of smaller schools' human resources, educators found themselves burdened by an excess of instructional responsibilities and supplementary tasks, impeding their ability to adequately attend to individual class needs, let alone fulfil their supplementary obligations, thereby impairing logistical challenges such as the production of printed reading materials (Tarraya, 2023).

Research suggested that the acquisition of reading skills was intricately linked to environmental factors, with studies indicating a significant correlation between reading achievement and the presence of literacy materials both at home and in educational settings. For instance, Huang et al., (2019) found a direct association between reading attainment and the accessibility of literacy resources. Therefore, these findings emphasized the critical importance of having abundant literacy materials within a reading remediation program, highlighting the necessity of rich resource environments in both program implementation and educational contexts.

Lack of Participatory Planning

Tailored fit materials were crucial for ensuring the validity of interventions by aligning content with individual learners' needs, thus enhancing comprehension and overall effectiveness (Afflerbach, 2018). Furthermore, personalized reading materials for reading interventions were crucial as they addressed individual learners' specific reading requirements, ensuring content alignment with proficiency levels, interests, and learning styles, thereby enhancing engagement, comprehension, and overall effectiveness of corrective efforts (Frankel and Pearson, 2014). Aside from tailored-fit reading materials, contextualized schedules should also be considered in developing a reading program.

The Strengthened Technical Vocational Education Program (STVEP) which was offered in the cluster under study, emphasized technical and vocational education, augmenting the standard six daily classes in regular high schools' schedules with an additional two hours devoted to specialized subjects (DepEd Order 67, 2012). This caused challenges to the reading coordinators in terms of providing a proper schedule of implementation suited to the tight schedules.

This necessitated the involvement of reading teachers in participatory planning with program heads to determine the effectiveness of the reading program in terms of its execution (Mubita et al., 2017).

Inappropriate Materials

This was not seen as a problem during the first year of intervention because the program was only focused on Grade 7 students (DepEd Davao City, 2021), hence, during the following year, when all grade levels (grades 7-12) were involved, and reading teachers were tasked with selecting reading material from the Phil IRI (Philippine Informal Reading Inventory), confusions had begun.

While the Phil-IRI served as a standardized tool for assessing reading abilities, its scope was limited to Elementary and Grade 7 levels (DepEd-BLR, 2018). Therefore, adaptations or additional assessment tools was necessary for evaluating reading proficiency in higher grade levels or other educational contexts.

The responses also highlighted the lack of standardized materials for reading assessment across grade levels, particularly noting the absence of resources for Grades 8 to 12, leading to challenges in administering a suitable pre-test due to the varying proficiency levels among students.

The significance of an appropriate reading assessment instrument was rooted in its capacity to guarantee the reliability of collected data, permit precise assessment of individuals' reading proficiencies, and guide efficacious instructional interventions (Dougherty Stahl et al., 2019). That was the reason why utilizing a reading assessment designed for Grade 7 across all grade levels raised doubts about its credibility. This situation underscored the necessity for diverse reading approaches and language assessments, as a uniform approach might not be suitable for all learners (Ashton, 2016). Additionally, an increased improvement in reading fluency occurred when reading instruction was customized and tailored to individual needs, especially their lexical level (Forster et al., 2018)

Scheduling Conflict

These were supported by the claim of an overly jammed-packed K-12 curriculum that needed revision (Galvez, 2023). The curriculum offerings of an arts and trade school encompassed various fields such as automotive technology, building construction, cosmetology, drafting, electronics, food trades, garments, machining, PC hardware servicing, plumbing, refrigeration and air-conditioning, and welding. This had caused overlapping responsibilities to reading teachers and other teachers concerned.

Furthermore, the transition to face-to-face learning had resulted in scheduling challenges due to overlapping activities, hindering the implementation of the program. The presence of multiple subjects further complicated the incorporation of reading activities into the curriculum, posing logistical difficulties for the implementers.

Lack of Training

Mentoring teachers was crucial for providing personalized support, guidance, and professional development opportunities to enhance their teaching skills and effectiveness (Vikaraman et al., 2017), especially that even non-language teachers were tasked to handle the 8-Week Reading Remediation Program.

The importance of teacher training programs in fostering effective literacy instruction was exemplified in the study by Ahmed et al., (2021), entitled "The Role of Teacher Training Programs in Optimizing Teacher Motivation and Professional Development Skills" wherein teacher training played a vital role in developing learners' reading skills by bolstering educators' confidence and fostering their professional growth, thereby equipping them with the pedagogical knowledge, instructional strategies, and assessment techniques necessary to effectively cultivate literacy development in their students.

Teacher's Participation

Similar to other professions, teachers needed to maximize their capabilities to deliver high-quality service and excel in their roles. Though it was only a school arrangement to involve non-language teachers participating in the implementation of the program, their roles were seen as vital to the reading program's success. Teacher collaboration strengthened program implementation by leveraging diverse perspectives, pooling resources, and facilitating effective problem-solving, ultimately enhancing student outcomes and fostering a culture of continuous improvement within the educational community (Schleifer, 2017).

Furthermore, remedial reading teachers needed to acquire essential knowledge and skills. The training in language skills was crucial as it would help them understand their teaching role better, making it easier to meet their professional needs effectively (Gatcho and Bautista, 2021).

By engaging educators from diverse subject areas, such as mathematics, science, and social studies, the reading program extended beyond traditional language instruction, fostering a cross-disciplinary approach to literacy education (Fisch and Chenelle, 2018). To provide teachers with the knowledge and techniques they need to create an engaging classroom and prevent mistakes in execution. Thus, thorough training programs on the implementation of the 8-Week Reading Remediation Program were crucial to avoid mistakes

Parental Involvement Deficiency

The responses underscored the crucial role of parental involvement and support in monitoring children's progress, guiding them in reading at home, and providing follow-up to reading activities, thereby addressing the challenge of lack of parental engagement in

student remediation efforts. To address this, parents should be seen as supports in reading intervention, where they provide sustenance to their children's literacy development by offering guidance, feedback, and encouragement during reading activities (Mermelshtine, 2017).

This active involvement also facilitated children's confidence, comprehension, and independence in reading, highlighting the crucial role of parental engagement in fostering literacy skills outside of the classroom. Reading skills could significantly be cultivated at home to contribute to students' academic achievement by fostering literacy proficiency and comprehension, crucial for success across various subjects and learning contexts (Castro, et al., 2015).

Student's absenteeism

The acknowledgment by reading coordinators of the challenge posed by student absenteeism underscored the urgency of addressing this issue. It was evident that reducing student absenteeism stood as a crucial factor in improving rates of foundational reading success among students (Anderson, 2022).

Improving the understanding of absenteeism involved identifying its underlying factors. Balkis et al. (2016) found that students' living conditions had a major influence on their attendance and participation in class; the majority of them came from low-income families. Unfortunately, absenteeism affected students' academic performance in addition to impeding their development as readers (Keppens, 2023).

Reading remediation programs were designed to cater to struggling readers. However, without the presence of these learners, the existence and implementation of it would not be successful. In addition, it was important to note that teachers often missed seeing the difficulties of students at home (Buck and Deutsch, 2014) due to different motives; one of the complications was poverty. It was undeniable that poverty was one of the reasons, making it the root cause of absenteeism in schools (Gee, 2018).

Communication Barriers

The difficulty of locating the learners hampered the process of providing them with reading materials and getting their completed answer sheets. Hence, the failure to effectively provide reading interventions resulted in poor performance in other learning areas such as Science and Mathematics as reflected in the recent Program for International Student Assessment (PISA) assessment for the years 2018 and 2019 (Servallos, 2023). In addition, poor reading skills could lead to disengagement, frustration, and a higher likelihood of dropping out of school due to limited academic success and opportunities for advancement, emphasizing the critical role of literacy proficiency in fostering educational persistence and achievement (Mar and Ancho, 2019).

Limited Program Monitoring

The reading coordinators and reading teachers underscored the need for higher-level authorities to be actively involved, suggesting collaborative efforts to address challenges and provide support, particularly in managing schedules and addressing operational constraints, so that the reading remediation program would be successfully implemented. Active program monitoring in schools was imperative for optimizing the effectiveness and efficiency of educational initiatives (Sanchez and Sarmiento, 2020).

Recognizing the pivotal role of monitoring in enhancing teacher performance through accountability and adherence to standards (Bunger et al., 2019), it becomes evident that effective monitoring could ultimately improve students' educational experiences by enhancing teacher effectiveness and engagement.

In the context of the 8-Week Reading Remediation in Cluster 9, identified as a rural area, assessment of program the implementation could have enabled administrators to identify areas for improvement and intervene promptly, ensuring accountability, fostering continuous improvement, and upholding standards of quality, all of which ultimately would contribute to enhancing student learning experiences and academic success.

Fabrication of Results

The risk of falsifying results in reading programs was alarming due to the breach of professional ethics, notably honesty, which was a cornerstone of the code of ethics for professional teachers. Such actions not only undermine the integrity of educational practices but also batter trust among stakeholders, potentially leading to disciplinary actions, tarnished reputations, and a compromised learning environment (Professional Regulation Commission, 2021). The making up of results was due to the pressure given to the coordinators to submit results as mandated.

This dishonesty had a significant impact on the accuracy of the findings. It should be noted that the importance of result reliability relied on its ability to ensure the accuracy, consistency, and validity of findings, thereby enhancing the credibility and trustworthiness of outcomes (Wang et al., 2004). Falsified results in a reading program dented the credibility of educational interventions and misinformed decision-making processes, which led to ineffective resource allocation and hindered student progress (Moran, 2022). Furthermore, falsified data demoralized stakeholders' trust, harming the educational institution's reputation and reducing support for future endeavors.

Implementation Deficiency

The provision of a feedback mechanism was vital as it provided valuable insights, identified areas for improvement, and ensured alignment with overarching goals, ultimately enhancing the effectiveness and efficiency of the initiative (Wisnieski et al., 2020). Moreover, in the absence of feedback, errors were likely to persist, and

deficiencies remained unaddressed, perpetuating a cycle of suboptimal performance and hindering opportunities for improvement (Dawson, et al., 2018).

The Philippine Professional Standards for Supervisors (PPSS) represented a cornerstone in the realm of supervisory practices, particularly concerning the facilitation of reading programs. Within this framework, Strand 3.1 assumed paramount importance, delineating the requisite competencies and responsibilities expected of supervisors tasked with overseeing reading initiatives (DepEd Order 25, 2020). By adhering to the guidelines outlined in Strand 3.1 of the PPSS, supervisors should effectively navigate the complexities inherent in managing reading programs, thereby fostering a conducive environment for literacy development and educational advancement among participants. This scholarly approach underscored the significance of integrating the PPSS within the context of reading program supervision, ensuring adherence to professional standards and best practices aimed at optimizing program outcomes.

Implementation Uniformity

This inconsistency underscored the need for coordinated efforts and clear communication among program supervisors to ensure equitable access to resources and optimize the effectiveness of the reading initiative (Honig and Rainey, 2019). Likewise, the challenge of ensuring a consistent method for recording and reporting results was identified as a significant obstacle requiring constructive feedback for resolution.

The reading teachers also emphasized the reputation of standardized templates for recording scores, suggesting that while teachers could manage independently, uniform monitoring methods would enhance effectiveness in tracking student progress. Furthermore, standardized templates for recording scores were crucial as they ensured consistency, accuracy, and efficiency in tracking student progress, facilitating informed decision-making, and promoting collaboration among stakeholders (Aase, et al., 2020).

Therefore, the directives from program heads to teachers should ensure the alignment with the program objectives and to empower teachers to adapt strategies according to student needs and to maximize the program's impact on literacy development (Bunger, et al., 2019). Incorporating regular feedback mechanisms and fostering a collaborative environment among educators could further enhance the effectiveness of the program. By systematically addressing these areas, schools could foster an environment where teachers feel equipped and supported to navigate the diverse challenges of program implementation.

In conclusion, the data analysis highlighted critical challenges affecting the 8-Week Reading Remediation Program's success. Key issues included insufficient funding, poor communication, and inadequate teacher training, leading to the use of unsuitable materials and misassigned roles. Scheduling difficulties and low parental involvement further exacerbate student absenteeism and inconsistent participation. Additionally, effective program monitoring was hindered by implementation deficiencies and inconsistent supplementary materials. These challenges collectively underscored the

need for targeted interventions to enhance the program and improve student literacy outcomes.

The Proposed Improvement to Enhance the 8-Week Reading Remediation Program

Resource Availability

The participants highlighted the importance of leveraging technology to enhance access to educational content and cater to student needs, aligning with contemporary pedagogical approaches aiming for inclusivity and personalized learning experiences. Consequently, integrating educational technology promoted better reading outcomes compared to traditional ones (Ni et al., 2022). This would enhance accessibility, engagement, and personalized learning experiences and foster literacy development in diverse educational settings.

Giving students access to concrete reading resources could improve their reading habits and interests (Kung, 2017). However, the provision of reading resources to students should not only be limited to print media but also consist of non-print materials.

The significance of tangible reading materials, such as books, over ordinary printed materials was underscored by participants, highlighting students' preference for holding physical books. This insight emphasized the importance of ensuring access to printed reading resources during the 8-Week Reading Remediation Program. By providing students with diverse reading materials, including both print and non-print resources, educators could potentially enhance students' reading habits and interests, contributing to the overall effectiveness of the program in fostering literacy development.

Program Collaboration

The collaboration of program implementers in the program's Development stage was essential given their invaluable expertise and insights necessary for devising tailored and effective strategies that met the diverse needs of students (Afflerbach, 2018). Collaborative efforts enabled teachers to collectively take ownership of program implementation, driving meaningful changes in instructional practices and promoting continuous improvement in reading remediation efforts (Voogt et al., 2018).

Additionally, proper representation of teachers in program planning could address key issues like providing appropriate learning materials for learners. According to Drits-Esser and Stark (2015), working together to share perspectives during program design improved comprehension and produced more effective treatments suited to a range of student requirements. Offering individualized reading materials for interventions implied a customized strategy to meet each student's unique reading demands.

To sum, participatory planning in program design could improve comprehension, engagement, and the efficacy of remedial efforts. Additionally, this underscored the importance of considering learners' proficiency levels, interests, and learning styles when designing the reading intervention, highlighting the potential impact on student outcomes and program efficacy (Frankel and Pearson, 2014).

Teachers' Training

The reading teachers underscored the importance of teacher training in fostering student enthusiasm for reading, enhancing vocabulary, and refining pronunciation skills. Effective training should be done to assess and address existing problems in the implementation and aid the queries stated by the reading teachers. In light of this, the Department of Education should offer more engaging training for teachers.

By giving teachers practical direction, individualized attention, and interactive learning opportunities, in-person teacher training could give reading program teachers and implementers the tools they need to meet the varied learning needs of their students (Heafner, 2022). By doing this, it would be possible to achieve collaborative and participatory planning and develop a cohesive strategy for meeting the needs of the learners.

Training at the school level was a great way to help language and non-language teachers implement the program. The use of SLAC, or School Learning Action Cell, could convene small groups of teachers regularly to reflect on teaching methods, share experiences, and develop strategies for improving learning outcomes.

Interdisciplinary teaching practices were perceived to be one of the most effective ways to enhance literacy skills and knowledge across different learning areas. This was one of the indicators in classroom observations in the year-end assessment of public-school teachers known as the Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form, or IPCRF (DM No. 008, s. 2023).

Using reading to subject integration, teachers could apply content knowledge within and across curriculum teaching areas. Furthermore, integration of reading across all subjects enhanced students' comprehension, critical thinking, and retention, fostering a holistic approach to learning while nurturing a lifelong love for reading (Blintz and Monobe, 2020).

Adjustment of Schedules

This reflected the participant's contemplation regarding the timing of implementing a reading program, expressing uncertainty about integrating it within or after the school year. Clearly, the teachers proposed that school administrators should reorganize schedules to incorporate reading activities effectively within the curriculum, given the demanding nature of their ten-subject structure and limited vacant time slots.

Reading as a Subject

This suggestion highlighted the identification of reading as a core ability and a subject or program that deserved dedicated instructional time. Regular reading increased one's vocabulary, fluency, and comprehension while fostering critical thinking skills and extending one's knowledge across a range of topics. Moreover, the quantity and quality of reading material with varying degrees of complexity was also a better strategy for improving overall reading and literacy, even though the amount of time spent reading was still considered a factor (Zebroff and Kaufman, 2017).

Parental Involvement

According to Iroegbu and Igweike (2020) there was a positive correlation between students' reading comprehension and parental involvement. In the same way that a positive community-school dynamic produced better results for students' well-being and development, increasing parental involvement in their children's reading development would help them succeed more. Thus, parental involvement in school-related activities such as reading would contribute to academic success (Castro et al., 2015).

Regular Program Monitoring

Regular monitoring was essential for enhancing teacher productivity by providing feedback, support, and tailored professional development opportunities to improve instructional practices and maximize student learning outcomes (Qurtubi, 2017). Similarly, progress monitoring among students' reading assessment was essential as it provided insights into individual learning trajectories, informed instructional decision-making, and enabled timely intervention strategies to address any emerging challenges or gaps in reading proficiency (Harper-Young and Harper-Young, 2018).

It might be that teachers experienced a pervasive culture of fear during visits by administrators or program heads since it was characterized by heightened anxiety and apprehension regarding potential evaluation and criticism of their performance (Agalday and Yigit, 2022), this was one way of providing technical assistance to teachers in enhancing program implementation and carrying out their duties and responsibilities (Sangalang, 2019). Nevertheless, the provision of regular program monitoring was crucial to ensuring consistency in providing guidance to the teachers and, in turn, improving the conduct of the reading remediation program.

Consistency of Feedback

This underscored the importance of establishing clear channels of communication between program heads and teacher implementers, highlighting the need for constructive feedback mechanisms throughout the implementation process. Additionally, it emphasized the significance of post-implementation feedback to facilitate reflection,

identify challenges, and inform future improvements in reading program delivery (Opiela, 2018).

The consistency of feedback not only played an important role to teachers, but also a critical move in providing students with timely and targeted support to enhance their reading skills and overall learning experience (Bastola and Hu, 2023).

Conclusions

Based on the aforementioned summary, the study concluded with the following implications:

1. The research underscored the pressing need for targeted interventions to address issues like insufficient resource allocation, lack of appropriate reading materials, and gaps in program design and execution.
2. The challenges hindered the effective delivery of reading remediation services and impeded student progress in literacy development.
3. Educational policymakers and stakeholders must prioritize allocating resources and support mechanisms to rectify these deficiencies, ensuring equitable access to quality reading materials and tailored interventions for students with diverse learning needs.
4. The identified gaps in teacher training, student engagement, and parental involvement emphasized the importance of comprehensive professional development programs and community outreach initiatives to foster a collaborative environment conducive to enhancing reading outcomes.
5. The proposed enhancements for the program, such as promoting teacher collaboration and integrating reading as a core subject, suggested avenues for innovation and improvement in literacy instruction methodologies.
6. Implementing the proposed enhancements could contribute to the overall effectiveness and sustainability of reading remediation efforts, thereby fostering a culture of literacy excellence within the educational system of Davao City.

Recommendations

Drawing from result, recommendations were developed as follows:

1. The School Reading Coordinators may provide training to reading teachers and non-language teachers to promote participation in the implementation of the program. Furthermore, they may design School Learning Action Cells (SLAC) sessions tailored for teacher training in reading, including both language and non-language mentors.

Furthermore, they may participate in professional development workshops and training sessions focused on evidence-based reading instruction and intervention techniques.

2. The Cluster Reading Coordinators may conduct tailored and culturally sensitive training workshops designed to elevate teachers' abilities in crafting personalized reading materials, thereby tackling concerns regarding material suitability and schedule flexibility. These materials would cater to schools with diverse schedules and curriculum offerings, fostering heightened student engagement and participation.
3. The Education Program Supervisor in English may advocate for additional budget allocation to schools to address the need for more photocopiers, printers, and ink supplies, thereby expediting the reproduction of materials. He/she may also develop in-person training programs which include participatory program planning and establish a timeline for regular monitoring of schools or clusters. To ensure consistent feedback and avoid the fabrication of data, the supervisor may utilize online or electronic systems for real-time monitoring, feedback, and reporting of results.
4. The English/Reading Teachers may engage in the training sessions facilitated by the Reading Coordinators to enhance their proficiency in supporting struggling readers. Additionally, they may establish provisions for regular parent conferences and establish communication mechanisms to address the problems in students' absenteeism using online, SMS or establishing partnerships with school stakeholders or LGUs to assist in locating students in need of remediation.
5. Future researchers may examine the effectiveness of localized reading materials on reading comprehension and engagement, considering variables like cultural relevance and individual differences, to provide comprehensive insights.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The following ethical considerations were followed before, during and after the conduct of the study.

Informed Consent. The researcher ensured that prior to conducting the interview, all participants were provided with and signed the informed consent form, detailing the purpose of the study, their rights as participants, and the voluntary nature of their involvement.

Vulnerability of the Research Participant. The researcher assured high confidentiality was also observed since the researcher had personal interaction with the participants through an interview. Aside from the aforementioned, subjects were neither mistreated

or abused, both physically and psychologically, during the interview. Also, the researcher aimed to create and sustain a comfortable environment.

Risks, Benefits and Safety. The researcher posed the risks and benefits of participating in this study. While discussing personal experiences during interviews may cause discomfort or emotional distress, contributing insights could potentially enhance educational programs and practices. Safety measures, including confidentiality and the option to withdraw at any time, will be implemented to mitigate risks. Overall, participation is voluntary, with participant safety being a top priority.

Privacy and Confidentiality. Participants were thoroughly briefed on the study's objectives and reassured that their responses would remain anonymous and confidential. They were informed that their input would be used solely for academic purposes and the specific research at hand, with strict adherence to ethical guidelines to safeguard their privacy.

Archiving the Data. The collected data would be securely archived for a designated period, adhering to ethical guidelines. Stored in password-protected electronic files or locked physical storage, access would be restricted to unauthorized personnel. Participants' confidentiality would be maintained, with identifying information removed. Additionally, the raw data would be deleted three (3) years following the study's publication date.

Acknowledgments

The researcher expresses profound gratitude and genuine appreciation to all individuals who have contributed to the successful completion of this study. Dr. Edilhynie M. Jambangan, his thesis adviser, for her unwavering guidance, invaluable insights, and steadfast support throughout the entirety of this research journey. Her expertise, encouragement, and constructive feedback have been instrumental in shaping the direction and refinement of this thesis. Dr. Ruby A. Serrano, TDAC Chair, for her unwavering support and guidance throughout the success of this paper. Dr. Rogelio D. Rasay III and Dr. Vivien Grace A. Jubahib, TDAC panel members, for their invaluable contributions, perceptive assessments, and helpful feedback, all of which have enhanced the caliber and thoroughness of this thesis, as well as for their dedication, patience, and mentorship.

Dr. Reynante A. Solitario, CESO V, the Davao School Division Superintendent, Public Schools District Supervisors and public-school Principals of Cluster 9, for their continuous assistance in facilitating the execution of the study through the cooperation of their English department heads/supervisors and English teachers. The participants of this study who willingly provided their willing support and extended their priceless time in partaking in the study. His Ampon National High School family, for the unwavering support and collaboration throughout this endeavor. Mr. Lyndon M. Dumael, Mr. Marlon A. Bernados and Ms. Carolyn D. Domingo, his principals, for their understanding, patience, guidance, and unwavering support throughout this undertaking. Cherlene R. Balderas, his beloved wife and Athaliah, his beautiful daughter, from whom he derives inspiration and strength during the trials and challenges encountered on this journey. The

researcher's parents, for the unwavering trust, confidence and support. On top of all, to the Almighty God, the source of all strength, love, mercy and wisdom.

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